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Influence of Contralateral and Ipsilateral Eye Vision on Non-Dominant Foot Skill Development in Beginner Male Soccer Players: A Parallel Study Design

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Abstract

The tactical dimension plays a dominant role in soccer performance. However, proper decision-making and the implementation of collective dynamics require strong soccer-specific skills, usually marked by solid lateral dominance. It remains unclear how eye dominance and lower limb laterality interact. This study assessed the influence of covering one eye (either ipsilateral or contralateral) on learning soccer skills with the non-dominant foot. Thirty-six beginner male players (aged 9.2 ± 1.1 years) were randomly assigned to one of three groups for 12 weeks: (i) practicing with the non-dominant foot while wearing an eyepatch on the ipsilateral eye, (ii) practicing with the non-dominant foot while wearing an eyepatch on the contralateral eye, and (iii) practicing with the non-dominant foot with both eyes open. Four skill tests were conducted: ball control, dribbling, passing, and shooting. Results showed that all groups improved from pre- to post-test, but there were no significant between-group differences in ball control, passing, or dribbling. Only the shooting test showed the superiority of the contralateral eye patch group. Overall, participants improved similarly across training conditions, indicating that non-dominant foot skill acquisition in beginners is largely robust to monocular vision. Patching one eye eliminates binocular disparity (stereopsis) while preserving monocular depth cues (e.g., motion parallax, occlusion, relative size) and forces greater reliance on haptic foot-ball feedback (Cutting & Vishton, 1995). The selective benefit observed in shooting accuracy therefore likely reflects enhanced compensatory use of these remaining cues in a task particularly dependent on precise 3D spatial localization.

Keywords: Motor Learning, Skill Acquisition, Visual Learning, Soccer Skills

Influence de la vision de l'œil contralatéral et ipsilatéral sur le développement des compétences du pied non-dominant chez les joueurs de football débutants masculins: Une étude en parallèle

Résumé

La dimension tactique joue un rôle dominant dans la performance au football. Cependant, une prise de décision appropriée et la mise en œuvre de dynamiques collectives nécessitent des compétences techniques spécifiques, généralement marquées par une forte dominance latérale. Il reste peu clair comment la dominance oculaire et la latéralité des membres inférieurs interagissent. Cette étude a évalué l'influence du recouvrement d'un œil (ipsilatéral ou contralatéral) sur l'apprentissage des habiletés footballistiques exécutées avec le pied non-dominant. Trente-six joueurs masculins débutants (âgés de $9,2 \pm 1,1$ ans) ont été aléatoirement répartis en trois groupes pendant 12 semaines : (i) entraînement du pied non-dominant avec cache-œil sur l'œil ipsilatéral, (ii) entraînement du pied non-dominant avec cache-œil sur l'œil contralatéral, et (iii) entraînement du pied non-dominant avec les deux yeux ouverts. Quatre tests de compétences ont été réalisés : contrôle de balle, dribble, passe et tir. Les résultats ont montré que tous les groupes se sont améliorés entre le pré- et le post-test, sans différences significatives entre groupes pour le contrôle de balle, la passe et le dribble. Seul le test de tir a révélé la supériorité du groupe avec cache-œil contralatéral. Globalement, les participants ont amélioré leurs compétences de manière similaire dans toutes les conditions, indiquant que l'acquisition de la technique du pied non-dominant chez les débutants est largement robuste à la vision monoculaire. Le recouvrement d'un œil élimine la disparité binoculaire (stéréopsie) tout en préservant les indices monoculaires de profondeur (parallaxe de mouvement, occultation, taille relative, etc.) et oblige à une plus grande dépendance au retour haptique pied-ballon (Cutting & Vishton, 1995). L'avantage sélectif observé sur la

précision du tir reflète donc probablement une meilleure exploitation compensatoire de ces indices résiduels dans une tâche particulièrement exigeante en localisation spatiale 3D précise.

Mots-clés: Apprentissage moteur, Acquisition de compétences, Apprentissage visuel, Football

Introduction

Soccer performance depends heavily on tactical skills, but every tactical decision must ultimately be executed through technical actions performed mainly with the feet ([Peker et al., 2022](#)). Because of strong lower-limb lateral preference, players overwhelmingly favour their dominant foot ([Carlsson et al., 2018](#); [Zago et al., 2014](#)). This creates two practical problems: opponents can predict actions more easily, and many game situations force the use of the non-dominant foot. Developing competent non-dominant-foot skills is therefore considered essential for versatility and long-term development ([Haaland & Hoff, 2003](#); [Rabello et al., 2022](#)).

Accurate execution of soccer skills, especially shooting and long passing, requires precise judgement of ball and target distances. Binocular vision supplies the strongest depth cue (binocular disparity) up to ~10 m, whereas monocular vision must rely on weaker but still effective cues (motion parallax, occlusion, relative size, height in the visual field) and on haptic foot–ball feedback ([Cutting & Vishton, 1995](#)).

The Constraints-Led Approach proposes that adding deliberate perceptual constraints during practice encourages athletes to explore new movement solutions and to rely more heavily on under-used sensory information ([Davids et al., 2008](#)). Similar visual-constraint methods, such as stroboscopic training, have already improved visuomotor performance in various sports ([Jothi et al., 2025](#)).

One previous study in basketball showed that acute occlusion of the sensory-dominant eye reduced free-throw accuracy ([Vera et al., 2020](#)). However, the free throw is a highly stereotyped, closed-skill task that differs markedly from the open-skill, variable actions typical of soccer. Moreover, the effects of chronic (multi-week) monocular training have never been examined.

The present exploratory study therefore investigated whether 12 weeks of non-dominant-foot training performed under monocular vision (ipsilateral or contralateral eye patched) would produce different learning outcomes compared with normal binocular training in beginner male soccer players aged 9-10 years. Four fundamental skills were assessed: ball control, dribbling, passing, and shooting. Particular interest was placed on shooting accuracy because this task places the highest demand on precise three-dimensional spatial judgement.

Materials and Methods

Participants

We calculated the study's power and sample size for each group using the statistical approach explored and G*Power 3.1 software (University of Dusseldorf, Dusseldorf, Germany). This analysis included the following: an a priori power analysis and F-tests to determine the achieved power; ANOVA for repeated measurements with within and between group interaction analysis; an α error probability of 0.05; a minimum effect size of 0.25; three groups; six measurement points; and a $1-\beta$ error probability of 0.80. With 24 participants, the study had an 80.1% probability of successfully rejecting the null hypothesis of no difference in variables, reflecting the actual statistical power (see Figure 1).

This study initially recruited 36 out of 41 volunteers (see Table 1), and randomly divided them into three groups using a computer-generated randomization table. All participants underwent a standard vision screening, including distance visual acuity (VA). The Dolman method (hole-in-card test) was used to measure eye dominance. Participants held a card with a tiny hole at arm's length and focused on a target; when the card was brought closer, the dominant eye was revealed

([Barbeito, 1981](#)). A total of 33 beginner male soccer players completed the intervention. The allocation sequence remained concealed until the intervention began (see Table 2).

****Table 1 near here****

For this study, several football schools in Isfahan were contacted, and 41 beginner male soccer players volunteered to participate. Of these, 36 players (mean age: 9.20 ± 1.05 years) met the eligibility criteria and were selected. The inclusion criteria required players to (1) have at least three months of football experience, (2) demonstrate a commitment to fully engage in all aspects of the study, and (3) agree to complete all training sessions. Players who missed test sessions were disqualified, leading to the exclusion of three participants. Their pre-test results showed no significant differences from the remaining players, and their absence was unrelated to the intervention. Because standing height, sitting height, and body mass can affect the development of motor skills, anthropometric data were gathered to determine maturity offset and guarantee group homogeneity ([Mirwald et al., 2002a](#)).

Each participant identified their dominant foot, defined as the one primarily used for shooting the ball ([Brophy et al., 2010](#); [Mulrey et al., 2020](#)). The study complied with the Helsinki Ethics Recommendations (2013 update), and parental informed consent was obtained before enrollment. Participants retained the right to withdraw from the study at any time. Ethical approval was granted by the Ethics Committee of the University of Mohaghegh Ardabili (12.08.2019).

****Figure 1 near here****

Experimental Approach

An experimental study was designed to assess whether the chronic use of a contralateral or ipsilateral eye while training with the non-dominant foot influences skill development in beginner

soccer players. The players were randomly assigned to one of three groups. Group one wore an eyepatch over the eye ipsilateral to their non-dominant foot and trained using the contralateral eye (NF/CE). Group two wore an eyepatch over the eye contralateral to their non-dominant foot and trained using the ipsilateral eye (NF/IE) ([Nachshon et al., 1983](#)). Group three served as the control group, training with their non-dominant foot while keeping both eyes open (CG). The exercises were explained to each group during training sessions, and the use of the eyepatch was demonstrated for the first two groups during a familiarization session. Training sessions were held three times per week for 12 weeks, each lasting approximately 50 minutes. Under the guidance of certified coaches to guarantee consistency, each session progressed in a planned manner, beginning with fundamental exercises (like stationary ball control) and moving on to more difficult assignments (like dynamic passing under pressure). Each session focused on four different types of training using the player's non-dominant foot under the conditions outlined in Table 1. All training sessions were identical across groups, and all participants followed the same structured training schedule throughout the intervention program.

****Table 2 near here****

Anthropometric measurements, including standing height, sitting height, and body mass were recorded for all participants in a single session before the start of the training program. Skill tests were conducted under similar conditions for all players, in the morning, with consistent weather conditions (~21-23°C and ~50% humidity). The same procedure was repeated for post-test measurements after 12 weeks of training, ensuring identical testing conditions.

Anthropometric measurements and skill tests were conducted before the 12-week intervention, with the skill tests repeated at the end of the program. During both pre- and post-testing, all skill tests were administered on a single day and in the same order. Players' ages at the

pre-test were recorded to two decimal places. All tests were conducted by assessors who were blinded to the intervention conditions.

Measurements and Tests

Anthropometric Data

To measure standing height, participants stood barefoot on a Seca® 213 stadiometer (Germany) with their heels as close to the stadiometer as possible, ensuring their hips and shoulder blades were aligned. For sitting height, participants sat on a 50 cm bench, positioning their hips as close to the stadiometer as possible. They maintained a straight posture with their hands resting on their feet. The Seca® 213 stadiometer was used with a measurement accuracy of 5 mm ([Eskandarifard et al., 2022](#)). Body weight was measured using the Seca® 813 scale (England) with an accuracy of 0.1 kg. Participants wore only sports shorts during the measurement ([Eskandarifard et al., 2022](#)). The following formula was used to calculate the maturity offset ([Mirwald et al., 2002b](#)).

$$\text{Maturity Offset} = -9.236 + (0.0002708 \times \text{Leg Length} \times \text{Sitting Height}) - (0.001663 \times \text{Age} \times \text{Leg Length}) + (0.007216 \times \text{Age} \times \text{Sitting Height}) + (0.02292 \times \text{Weight-Height Ratio})$$

Where: Leg Length is calculated as: Leg Length = Standing Height (cm) – Sitting Height (cm). The formula has a correlation coefficient of $R = 0.94$, an R^2 value of 0.89, and a Standard Error of Estimate (SEE) = 0.592.

Skill Tests

Four of the six football skill tests proposed by the Portuguese Football Federation were selected to assess players' abilities in this study: ball control with the body, dribbling accuracy and

speed, passing, and shooting ([Coelho e Silva et al., 2004](#); [Seabra et al., 2001](#)). All tests were conducted on artificial outdoor turf, with no prior familiarization. Before testing, players completed a 15-minute standardized warm-up consisting of stretching and dynamic movements, under the coach's supervision. Rest periods were provided between tests to prevent fatigue.

Skill Test One: Control The Ball with The Body

In a 9×9 square, the player began juggling the ball without using their hands or arms, attempting to keep it in the air. The test continued until the ball either touched the ground or made contact with the hands. The score was determined by the number of consecutive kicks the player performed while keeping the ball in the air. Each player was allowed one practice trial before the test. They then completed the test three times, with their best recorded score used as the final result (Figure 2a).

Skill Test Two: Dribble Accuracy and Speed

In a 9×9 square, four markers were placed in a straight line at a distance of 2.25 meters from each other. At the fifth mark, a bench lying on its side was placed at the end of the line. The player zigzagged between the first four markers, passed the ball to the bench, and then returned to the starting line in the same manner. The player had to complete this route at maximum speed without hitting the markers. If a player touched a marker, a 1-second was added to their total time as a penalty. The record for this test was the total duration in seconds. To measure the time, two stopwatches were used, both starting simultaneously at the instructor's signal. The average of the two recorded times was taken as the final result (Figure 2b).

Skill Test Three: Pass

Five targets were placed on one side of a 9×9 square, with a 2.5-meter distance between them. The player stood on the opposite side of the marks, outside the square with the ball. Each player had two attempts per target, for a total of ten attempts. The objective was to hit the targets with the ball, earning 2 points for each successful hit, with a maximum possible score of 10 points (Figure 2c).

Skill Test Four: Shot

A 2×3-meter goal was placed at the end of a 9×9 square and divided into six sections using ropes. A horizontal rope was tied 1.5 meters from the ground. while, vertical ropes were positioned 0.5 meters from each goalpost. The player had five attempts to kick the ball from outside the 9×9 square. Points were awarded based on where the ball entered the goal: 5 points for the top left or right sections, 3 points for the bottom left or right sections, 2 points for the top central section, and 1 point for the bottom central section ([Padron-Cabo et al., 2019](#)). No points were awarded if the ball missed the goal. The maximum possible score was 25 points (Figure 2d).

****Figure 2 near here****

Statistical Analysis

The reliability of this skill test battery was assessed using repeated-measures variance analysis (ANOVA) and intraclass correlation. A test-retest was conducted 48 hours after the initial examination, and the results were analyzed accordingly. The intraclass correlation coefficients (ICCs) were as follows: 0.78 for ball control with the body (skill 1), 0.81 for dribbling with a pass (skill 2), and 0.70 for both passing (skill 3) and shooting (skill 4). These reliability coefficients indicate an acceptable level of reliability ([Malina et al., 2005](#)). Since these tests assess fundamental

soccer skills, they have been validated. Additionally, their validity is supported by moderate correlations between the six trials of the Portuguese Football Federation (1986) and soccer tests involving slalom dribbling and wall volleying ([Coelho e Silva et al., 2004](#)).

Since the study followed a 3 (three groups) \times 2 (pre-post times) mixed design, data were analyzed using a univariate General Linear Model (GLM). The Levene's test was used to assess the homogeneity of variances. Effect sizes were determined using partial eta squared (η_p^2), with the following thresholds: trivial (0.01), small (0.01–0.06), moderate (0.06–0.14), and large (>0.14). Pairwise comparisons were conducted using Tukey's HSD test. The alpha level was set at $p \leq 0.05$. Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS software, version 22.

Results

Data analysis of the four skills revealed significant main effects of time ($p \leq 0.001$, $F = 32.40$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.52$), for the control skill. However, there was no significant group-by-time interaction ($p = 0.162$, $F = 1.93$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.11$). For passing skill, significant main effects of time were observed ($p = 0.001$, $F = 14.45$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.36$), but group-by-time interaction was not significant ($p = 0.601$, $F = 0.52$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.03$). Similarly, dribbling skill showed significant main effects of time ($p \leq 0.001$, $F = 39.12$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.57$), but no significant group-by-time interaction ($p = 0.673$, $F = 0.40$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.02$). Of the four skill tests, only shooting skill exhibited both significant main effects of time ($p \leq 0.001$, $F = 19.69$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.40$) and a significant group by time interaction ($p = 0.012$, $F = 5.18$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.26$). The results of the GLM analysis are presented in Table 3.

****Table 3 near here****

For comparing the development of the shooting variable, pairwise comparisons of the group mean across time (pre-test, post-test) revealed a significant increase in shooting between the

pre-test and post-test for the training with the non-dominant foot and contralateral-eye (NF/CE) group, as well as the training with the non-dominant foot and ipsilateral eye (NF/IE) group ($p = 0.036$). A significant difference was also observed between the NF/CE group and the control group ($p = 0.020$). However, the most significant difference was observed in the NF/CE group compared to the other groups, indicating that the most substantial development occurred in the NF/CE group ($p < 0.01$) (Table 4).

****Table 4 near here****

Furthermore, the univariate repeated measures can be seen in Figure 2. Figure 3 illustrates the development of control (Figure 3a), dribbling (Figure 3b), passing (Figure 3d), and shooting (figure 3c). Figure 3d clearly shows the improvement in shooting skill in the NF/CE group compared to the other two groups after 12 weeks.

****Figure 3 near here****

Discussion

This study aimed to assess the impact of covering one eye on the learning of soccer skills using the non-dominant foot in a sample of youth male soccer players. Given the novelty of the topic, we treated this study as exploratory and did not set formal hypotheses regarding the direction or magnitude of the effects. Four soccer skill tests were conducted (i.e., control, dribble, pass, and shot), all of which showed improvement by the end of the 12-week intervention compared to baseline. However, the only between-group difference at the end of the intervention was observed in the shooting test, where the group training with the non-dominant foot and contralateral eye of non-dominant foot (NF/CE) showed greater improvements than both the group training with the ipsilateral eye of non-dominant foot (NF/IE) and the control group (CG). The selective advantage in the shooting task aligns closely with known differences in depth information between binocular

and monocular viewing. Accurate shooting requires precise 3D localisation of the goal, a process heavily reliant on binocular disparity (stereopsis). In contrast, ball control, dribbling, and short-distance passing can be executed largely using monocular pictorial cues and haptic feedback ([Cutting & Vishton, 1995](#)). Chronic monocular training therefore appears to have promoted compensatory weighting of these remaining cues and increased reliance on tactile information from foot–ball contact, yielding a measurable benefit only when fine depth judgement was critical. Similar visual-constraint training using stroboscopic glasses has also been shown to improve visuomotor performance in athletes ([Jothi et al., 2025](#)). Therefore, two potentially contradictory findings emerged: (i) on one hand, practicing with the non-dominant foot while covering the contralateral eye seemed to enhance shooting accuracy; (ii) on the other hand, the effort of covering one eye did not appear to offer any advantages over the control group in three out of the four skill tests measured.

Improved eye-foot coordination and visuospatial processing in monocular situations may be the cause of the NF/CE group's higher shot accuracy. By aligning the visual input with the hemisphere that typically controls the non-dominant foot, contralateral ocular closure may enable more accurate motor planning ([Gonzalez & Niechwiej-Szwedo, 2016](#)). Shooting necessitates accurate aim at particular goal areas, which may be more sensitive to visual restrictions than the other skills assessed. Monocular vision's diminished depth perception might have made players rely more on proprioceptive feedback and spatial memory, which would have improved their capacity to adjust to the demands of the job ([Natsuhara et al., 2020](#)). This is consistent with the Constraints-Led Approach, which explores alternate movement solutions based on sensory restrictions ([Davids et al., 2008](#); [Schollhorn et al., 2010](#)).

Given the asymmetric nature of eye dominance (both visual and motor) ([Barbeito, 1981](#); [Higenbottam, 1975](#)) and considering the cortical architecture of the visual system ([Porac & Coren,](#)

[1976](#)), it is reasonable to question whether practicing foot skills with the non-dominant foot is influenced differently by occluding either the ipsilateral or the contralateral eye. Such insights could assist coaches in designing more effective practice constraints to maximize the development of foot skills with the non-dominant foot. Our results provide a clear message: for most foot skills (except shooting accuracy), patching one eye whether ipsilateral or contralateral does not appear to offer a significant advantage over practicing without an eye patch. Therefore, it may be that simply practicing with the non-dominant foot is the most important factor, and complex visual strategies or constraints may not greatly enhance learning or performance. However, the NF/CE group's notable gain in shooting accuracy raises the possibility that contralateral occlusion could improve certain skills requiring high visuospatial precision, perhaps by enforcing compensating sensory adjustments or enhancing hemisphere coordination ([Schollhorn et al., 2010](#)). Nonetheless, *occasional* practice with one eye patched could still be beneficial in breaking monotony or promoting differential learning. These findings also suggest that the results reported by Vera et al ([Vera et al., 2020](#)). May be task- and/or population-specific, and further research is needed. Notably, while the basketball study ([Vera et al., 2020](#)) assessed the acute effects of practicing with one eye patched, our study reflects the longer-term use of such strategies. It's possible that players may *habituate* to the visual occlusion and develop compensatory strategies.

A major limitation of our study is the absence of a familiarization period with the tests before starting the intervention. This implies that improvements from pre- to posttest may be partially attributed to increased familiarity with the tests. However, this would only account for overall differences over time and not between-group differences unless we consider that the tests lacked the sensitivity to detect tactical evolution, as previously mentioned. Another limitation is the early absence of eye dominance evaluation, which has since been fixed later and may have made the relationships between eye dominance and training circumstances clearer. While eye

dominance is relevant, it does not directly affect the relationship between covering the eye ipsilateral or contralateral to the dominant lower limb. Since each cerebral hemisphere primarily controls the contralateral side of the body, covering either the ipsilateral or contralateral eye may have a greater impact than simply covering the dominant eye. Additionally, while the dominant eye is typically associated with superior central accuracy, the non-dominant eye may function as a dynamic “driver”, enhancing peripheral movement detection, which is crucial in team sports. Based on our findings, we suggest that these novel interventions be applied sparingly within a framework of multilateral and diversified training to prevent excessive monotony caused by overly specific drills. To properly capture tactical and technical exchanges, future studies should investigate larger samples, players with different skill levels, and more ecological assessments, like small-sided games. Furthermore, research ought to look into particular facets of eye dominance (such as sight, motor, and sensory) and how these affect other soccer skills.

However, we strongly advocate for the consistent development of both the dominant and non-dominant foot, enabling players to access a wider range of movement solutions and increasing adaptability to various game scenarios. Future research should recruit larger samples to explore more complex interactions between different aspects of eye dominance (e.g., sight, motor, and sensory dominance) and foot preference (e.g., preference across all soccer actions or only specific skills).

In conclusion, while we strongly encourage the systematic development of non-dominant foot skills, complex visual constraints such as eye patching are not essential for most technical improvements in beginner players, although contralateral patching may offer a selective benefit for shooting accuracy in tasks requiring precise depth judgment.

Abbreviations

VA: Visual Acuity

Dominant Foot: Foot preferentially used for shooting the ball

NF/CE: Non-Dominant Foot, Contralateral Eye

NF/IE: Non-Dominant Foot, Ipsilateral Eye

CG: Control Group (both eyes open)

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Table 1

Descriptive statistics of participants

	NF/CE	NF/IE	CG
Right Foot /Left Foot (n)	11 (9/2)	12 (9/3)	10 (8/2)
Right Eye / Left Eye (n)	11(8/3)	12(9/3)	10(7/3)
Soccer Age Training (month)	14.73±9.58	14.00±8.66	17.00±6.81
Age (year)	9.22±0.86	9.35±1.15	8.99±1.19
Height (cm)	129.55±9.69	132.25±9.11	127.70±9.44
Sitting Height (cm)	70.27±4.38	70.00±5.18	68.70±4.66
Body Mass (Kg)	26.96±5.48	26.68±6.65	25.80±5.17

Table 2

Each session training program

Warm-up (10 minutes)	Juggling (10 minutes)	Running with the ball (10 minutes)	Passing (10 minutes)	Shooting (10 minutes)
Jogging	Juggling with	Slalom running	Hit the five	Shot to the goal
Stretching	balls and try to	with the ball,	marks (2.5	from a distance
Agility	keep the ball in	between eight	apart) with the	of 9 meters
	the air by kicking	marks (2.5	ball from 9	(goal division
		apart) in the	meters distance	was like shot
		direct line back		test)
		and forth		

Training sessions were the same in all groups just eyepatch was different. In the NF/CE group eyepatch was placed in the ipsilateral eye, in the NF/IE eyepatch was placed in the contralateral eye, and in the CG, there was no eyepatch in the eyes.

NF/CE: train with non-dominant foot and contralateral eye of the non-dominant foot;

NF/IE: train with non-dominant foot and ipsilateral eye of the non-dominant foot; CG:

Control group train with non-dominant foot and both eyes.

Table 3

Results of parameters in interaction with groups General Linear Model

Parameter	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig	Partial η_p^2	Noncent parameter	Observe d power
Control	8.045	2	4.023	1.829	0.179	0.112	3.658	0.350
Dribbling	1.283	2	0.641	0.480	0.624	0.032	0.960	0.121
Pass	1.739	2	0.870	0.316	0.732	0.021	0.632	0.095
Shot	46.305	2	23.152	5.201	0.012 *	0.264	10.401	0.788

* *Demonstrates a significant different between groups at $p < 0.05$.*

Table 4

HSD Tukey pairwise comparisons in shooting skills

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig	95% Confidence Interval for Difference	
					Lower	Upper
NF/CE	NF/IE	2.366	1.076	0.036 *	0.166	4.567
	Control	2.768	1.129	0.020 *	0.459	5.078
NF/IE	NF/CE	-2.366	1.076	0.036 *	-4.567	-0.166
	Control	0.402	1.113	0.721	-1.875	2.679
Control	NF/CE	-2.768	1.129	0.020 *	-5.078	-0.459
	NF/IE	-0.402	1.113	0.721	-2.679	1.875

*A significant difference between groups is observed at $p < 0.05$.

NF/CE: Training with the non-dominant foot while covering the contralateral eye.

NF/IE: Training with the non-dominant foot while covering the ipsilateral eye.

CG: Control group, training with the non-dominant foot with both eyes open.

Figure 1

Flow of the participant recruitment

Figure 2

Technical tests: (a) Controlling the ball with the body, (b) Dribbling accuracy and speed, (c) Passing, (d) Shooting. Legend: X = Player, O = Ball. ----- = Running with the ball

Figure 3

Development of the dependent variables across groups over time: (a) Development of control skill, (b) Development of dribbling skill, (c) Development of passing skill, (d) Development of shooting skill. NF/CE: Training with the non-dominant foot and contralateral eye of the non-dominant foot; NF/IE: Training with the non-dominant foot and ipsilateral eye of the non-dominant foot; CG: Control group, training with the non-dominant foot and both eyes

